

The Effect of Transformational Leadership Style, Work Environment, and Organizational Culture on Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) With Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable

Study on Educational Staff of Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq State Islamic University of Jember

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the influence of transformational leadership style, work environment, and organizational culture on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) with satisfaction as an intervening variable on educational staff at Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq State Islamic University of Jember. The population in this study was 171 educational staff. The number of samples was determined using the Yamane formula with a tolerance of 5% so that 119 respondents were obtained. The sampling technique used was simple random sampling. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to all respondents. The data source used is a primary source. The analysis method uses SEM PLS analysis with the WarpPLS 7.0 research tool. The results of the direct influence test showed that transformational leadership style has a significant effect on satisfaction but does not have a significant effect on OCB, the work environment has a significant effect on satisfaction but does not have a significant effect on OCB, organizational culture has a significant effect on satisfaction and OCB, and satisfaction has a significant effect on OCB. In the indirect influence test, it shows that transformational leadership style and work environment do not have a significant effect on OCB through satisfaction; organizational culture has a significant effect on OCB through satisfaction.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership Style, Work Environment, Organizational Culture, OCB, Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resource management is essential to increasing the effectiveness of resources in an organization or company. According to Dessler, employees (men) are one of the elements of management; human resources are very important for the success of the organization [1]. Good employee behavior in accordance with organizational rules will enable the organization to achieve the predetermined vision and mission. According to Markozy [2], good employees (good citizens) tend to display organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) in their work environment, so that the organization will be better with employees who act organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is the contribution of workers "above and beyond" formal job descriptions [2]. Organizational citizenship behavior is employee behavior that is permissive, cooperative, and voluntary, but employee behavior cannot be directly scanned in a formal work system [3]. Organizational citizenship behavior is behavior beyond the work responsibilities of an employee in working that is positive and based on awareness, sincerity, and without coercion.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior can be done by anyone, including employees of higher education institutions. Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq State Islamic University of Jember is an organization in the form of a state university in Kaliwates District, Jember Regency, East Java. Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq State Islamic University of Jember is a State Islamic Religious University that upholds moderate Islamic knowledge of the

archipelago by maintaining local wisdom as its characteristic. The location of Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq State Islamic University of Jember, hereinafter referred to as UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq of Jember, is located quite close to residential areas. In practice, UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq of Jember has employees who are divided into 2 (two) different main tasks: the first is educational staff employees called lecturers, where their main task is to plan learning, assess learning outcomes, carry out guidance tasks, and carry out research; and the second is educational staff, namely employees who have the main task of implementing administrative plans along with other technical matters that can support education at the university. UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq of Jember employees get the same facilities, rooms, parking lots, and responsibilities, namely to jointly realize the university's vision and mission. The results of a brief interview by researchers with several male and female students from all faculties at UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq of Jember got the answer that the quality of educational staff at UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq Jember has not yet reached the desired target, so it needs to be improved again.

There are several factors that can influence organizational citizenship behavior in an organization or company; these factors include transformational leadership, work environment, organizational culture, and employee job satisfaction [2]. In a study found that transformational leadership has a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior through job satisfaction [4,5,6]. However, in other study found different results that transformational leadership does not have a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior through job satisfaction [7 & 8]. The work environment is something that can create comfort for employees. A pleasant work environment will have a good impact on employees so that employees get satisfaction in achieving their performance and the company also achieves the company's goals that it wants to achieve [9]. The research about the effect of work environment on OCB through job satisfaction found that the work environment affects organizational citizenship behavior through job satisfaction [9,10,11,12], but there are different research results where the work environment does not affect organizational citizenship behavior through job satisfaction [3].

According to Luthans [13], organizational culture is the norms and values that guide the behavior of organizational members. Each member will behave according to the prevailing culture in order to be accepted by their environment. Organizational culture is unable to influence organizational citizenship behavior through job satisfaction [7]. In another study was found that organizational culture influences organizational citizenship behavior through job satisfaction [14 & 15].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

Leadership is the ability to influence others, subordinates, or groups and the ability to direct the behavior of subordinates or groups [16]. Leadership is a classic topic of discussion, but it is still very interesting to study because it greatly determines the progress of an organization. Robbins and Judge stated that transformational leaders are leaders who inspire their followers to put aside their personal interests for the good of the organization, and they are able to have an extraordinary influence on their followers [2]. Transformational leaders are visionary leaders who invite the organization's human resources to move towards the vision held by the leader [17]. Sivanathan explains that transformational leaders rely more on charisma and authority in carrying out their leadership. Transformational leaders are leaders who provide the organization's vision and mission appropriately and encourage team members to trust and respect each other [18]. The indicators of transformational leadership style according from Bass are idealized influence, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration [2].

Work Environment

According to Sedarmayanti, the work environment is a place for a number of groups where there are several supporting facilities to achieve company goals in accordance with the company's vision and mission [19]. The work environment is everything that is around employees and can influence employees in carrying out their duties and work every day [10]. The work environment is something that can create comfort for

employees. The indicators of work environment are lighting, air temperature, noise, cleanliness, security, color, relationship between co-workers at same level and relationship between boss [20].

Cultural Organization

According to Luthans, organizational culture is the norms and values that guide the behavior of organizational members. Each member will behave according to the prevailing culture in order to be accepted by their environment [13]. Robbins and Judge explain that organizational culture is a shared perception held by members of the organization or a shared system that is valued by the organization. Robbins and Judge said that there are 7 indicators of organizational culture, Innovation and risk taking, Attention to detail, Outcome orientation, People orientation, Team orientation, Aggressiveness, and Stability [4].

Job Satisfaction

Robbins and Judge said job satisfaction is a positive feeling about a person's work that is the result of evaluating its characteristics [21]. Job satisfaction is important in an organization because job satisfaction has a positive impact on organizational effectiveness. Gibson stated that job satisfaction is an attitude of workers regarding their work, which is the result of their perception of their work based on factors in the work environment such as supervisory style, policies and procedures, work group affiliation, working conditions, and other benefits for workers [22]. Luthans stated job satisfaction has 4 (four) indicators, there are The work itself, Salary/pay, Advancement chance/promotion, Supervision, Coworkers [23].

Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Cichorzewska argues that organizational citizenship behavior is behavior that is not included in the employment contract or job description and is beneficial to the organization [6]. Robbins and Judge state that organizational citizenship behavior is a work behavior displayed by employees in an organization that is carried out voluntarily outside the established job description to improve performance progress [4]. Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is an individual's contribution that exceeds the demands of the role in the workplace, which includes behavior in helping others, volunteering for extra work, and complying with the rules and procedures in the workplace [2]. The OCB indicators that are widely known and used in research are the organizational citizenship behavior dimensions proposed by Organ which consist of Altruism, Courtesy, Sportmanship, Civic virtue, Conscientiousness [5].

III. RESEARCH METHOD

This research is categorized as confirmatory research as well as explanatory research. This is because this research intends to test and explain the causal relationship between variables through testing the formulated hypothesis. The influence of the variables in question is the exogenous variable, namely transformational leadership, work environment, cultural organizational, intervening satisfaction variables, and endogenous variables, namely OCB. The analysis method uses SEM PLS analysis with the WarpPLS 7.0 research tool. This study has 119 samples of educational staff employees at UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq of Jember. Testing was carried out using the Warp-PLS application with the output in Table 1 as follows:

Table of direct and indirect effect

Variable	Direct path coef.	p-Value	Results
TL => JS	0,153	0,043	Positive and Significant
WE => JS	0,206	0,010	Positive and Significant
CO => JS	0,479	<0,001	Positive and Significant
TL => OCB	-0,020	0,414	Negative and Not Significant
WE => OCB	0,088	0,160	Positive and Not Significant
CO => OCB	0,503	<0,001	Positive and Significant

JS => OCB	0,380	<0,001	Positive and Significant
TL =>JS => OCB	0,058	0,182	Positive and Not Significant
WE=>JS => OCB	0,078	0,110	Positive and Not Significant
CO =>JS => OCB	0,182	0,002	Positive and Significant

Source: Data processed by authors(2024)

IV. RESULTS

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Job Satisfaction

The path coefficient value of transformational leadership (X1) on job satisfaction (Z) is 0.153 with a positive value. The p-value = 0.043, which means significant because the p-value <0.05. It can be concluded that H1 is accepted where transformational leadership is a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The Effect of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction

The path coefficient value of the work environment (X2) on job satisfaction (Z) is 0.206 with a positive value. The p-value = 0.010 is significant because the p-value <0.05. It can be concluded that H2 is accepted where work environment is a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction.

The Effect of Cultural Organization on Job Satisfaction

The results of the hypothesis test found that organizational culture has a significant effect on the satisfaction of educational staff at UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq Jember. The path coefficient value of organizational culture (X3) on job satisfaction (Z) is 0.479 with a positive value. The p-value = <0.001; this result is significant because the p-value <0.05. It can be concluded that H3 is accepted where there is a significant influence.

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on OCB

The path coefficient value of transformational leadership style (X1) on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) is -0.020, which is negative. The p-value = 0.414, which means it is not significant because the p-value is >0.05. It can be concluded that there is an insignificant influence, so H4 is rejected. Result of this study state that transformational leadership style does not have a significant effect on OCB.

The Effect of Work Environment on OCB

The results of the hypothesis test, it shows that the work environment has not a significant effect on OCB. The path coefficients of the work environment (X2) on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) are 0.088 with a positive value. The p-value = 0.160; this result is not significant because the p-value is >0.05. It can be concluded that there is an insignificant effect, so H5 is rejected.

The Effect of Cultural Organization on OCB

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it shows that the cultural organization has a significant effect on OCB. This is indicated by the path coefficient value of organizational culture (X3) on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) is 0.503 with a positive value. The p-value = <0.001; this result is significant because the p-value <0.05. It can be concluded that H6 is accepted where there is a significant influence.

The Effect of Job Satisfaction on OCB

The path coefficient value of job satisfaction (Z) towards organizational citizenship behavior (Y) is 0.380, which is positive. The p-value = <0.001. This result is significant because the p-value <0.05. It can be concluded that H7 is accepted where there is a significant influence. The result of the hypothesis test show that satisfaction has a significant influence on the organizational citizenship behavior of educational staff at UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq Jember.

The Effect of Transformational Leadership on OCB through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable

Based on the results of the hypothesis test, it shows that the path coefficient value of transformational leadership (X1) on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) through job satisfaction (Z) is 0.058 with a positive value. The p-value is 0.182, which means it is not significant because the p-value is >0.05 . It can be concluded that H8 is rejected where there is no significant influence. The results of the hypothesis test show that transformational leadership style does not have a significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior of educational staff at UIN Kiai Haji Achmad Siddiq Jember through satisfaction.

The Effect of Work Environment on OCB through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable

The path coefficient value of the work environment (X2) on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) through job satisfaction (Z) is 0.078 with a positive value. The p-value = 0.110 is significant because the p-value is >0.05 . It can be concluded that H9 is rejected where there is no significant influence.

The Effect of Cultural Organization on OCB through Job Satisfaction as an Intervening Variable

The path coefficient value of organizational culture (X3) on organizational citizenship behavior (Y) through job satisfaction (Z) is 0.182 with a positive value. The p-value = 0.002. This result is significant because the p-value <0.05 . So it can be concluded that H10 is accepted where there is a significant influence.

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